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EFFECTIVENESS OF WHATSAPP AS A TOOL TO ENHANCE ENGLISH-SPEAKING SKILLS OF UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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Abstract

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The primary purpose of this research is to explore the effectiveness of WhatsApp as a tool to enhance the English-speaking skills of university students, addressing the need for additional language practice beyond limited in-class opportunities. Since there is limited time available in class to practice speaking English, students often find it difficult to become proficient in oral communication. Students especially face this problem in settings where English is not the primary language. Students may not have enough opportunity to participate, and meaningful spoken instruction in traditional classroom settings could leave a gap in their capacity to communicate effectively in English. To get reliable outcomes and draw valid conclusions from the study, the quantitative research approach is employed throughout the data collection and analysis. This study's results demonstrate that WhatsApp enhances students' fluency, which has been reflected in the pre- and posttest analyses showing a notable increase in vocabulary, lexical competence and grammar among participants. These findings affirm that WhatsApp's informal and interactive setting provides students with continuous exposure to new vocabulary, supporting vocabulary development, grammar and fluency beyond the classroom. This study recommends that English language curriculum designers integrate WhatsApp and similar mobile assistant tools into their programs to extend language learning beyond the classroom. Future research should investigate the effectiveness of WhatsApp-based language learning activities across different skill levels and age groups. Such studies could provide insights into the specific benefits of mobile learning tools for diverse learner profiles.

Keywords: WhatsApp, Language learning, English, Speaking Skills, University Students.

Introduction

One of the linguistic skills used in daily life is speaking. Speaking is the preferred method of communication because it is more successful when done this way. Speaking is a crucial part of communication because it allows one to properly express, state and convey ideas, thoughts or feelings to others by producing sounds or words in a spoken language that is understandable to others (Widiastuti et al., 2019). Speaking skills are a linguistic ability that's critical for community communication. Humans use speaking as a language action to express and communicate with one another (Buton & Astuti, 2000). One may argue that speaking is a type of human behavior that draws on linguistic, psychological, neurological, and physical aspects. Moreover, speaking is a technique for conveying concepts that have been gathered and developed by the listener's demands (Mantra et al., 2018).

Speaking is a tool that almost immediately reveals to the listener whether or not the speaker understands the subject matter of the discussion and the listeners, whether or not he is adaptable in the way he presents his opinions, and whether or not he is focused and enthusiastic. Speaking abilities are therefore the primary building block of language since they are: (1) the most widely used way of expression; (2) the first skill that children typically acquire; and (3) the most common type of language skills. It may be argued that for kids to talk correctly, they need to acquire a variety of language skills. As a result, speaking abilities should continuously advance in kids (Mantra et al., 2018).

Consequently, a variety of initiatives, including parental support, should be used to continuously develop pupils' speaking abilities. Additionally, to ensure that students are actively learning to speak, teachers must incorporate suitable learning activities (Amelia, 2019). Incorporating communication technology into education is one of the ways that learning may be done. Given that students

are used to utilising WhatsApp for daily communication, WhatsApp groups are thought to be an efficient method of instruction (Elhadi, 2018). According to Gamage et al. (2020), the spread of COVID-19 and the introduction of online learning have increased public exposure to the application of communication technologies in education. By employing online or remote learning resources, educators and learners can continue to interact and complete the English language learning process without physically meeting in person (Ariebowo, 2021). With all its benefits and drawbacks, this approach is thought to be the most beneficial and is probably to be used in the current crisis. To attain optimal learning objectives and facilitate efficient material delivery, a teacher must possess the ability to develop their creativity to make the most of online media for English language learning.

For those learning English as a second language (ESL), gaining confidence when speaking the language is essential to improving their language skills. An increased sense of self-assurance helps a learner communicate both in their home tongue and the target language more precisely and fluently (Gurler, 2015). Given the close relationship between engagement and learning, it could be challenging for students to develop speaking confidence in their second language without sufficient interaction (Akkara et al., 2020). To engage in conversation, students should be able to successfully converse through a variety of media with others who are English language learners. The current generation has been greatly impacted by huge developments in technology. Unquestionably, technology has impacted our lives, bringing about amazing advancements in education and swift developments (Amelia, 2020).

ESL students today are more familiar with the use of modern technology in education because they were born into the digital era. As noted by Mustafa (2018), in the middle of the greatest technological transformation to date,

today's students, referred to as the "Next Generation" or digital natives, face novel hurdles in learning. In addition, learners should have access to more interesting materials that will aid in the development of their speaking abilities and increase their confidence when conversing with others in a second language. Many studies have examined the possibilities of the newly available technological tools for teaching second languages in the language-learning setting as a result of their increased attention (Kartal, 2019). According to Jasrial (2019), one of the most effective methods for teaching and learning the English language is mobile technology, often known as mobile-assisted language learning, or MALL. These days, owning a smartphone—either a personal or shared one—is typical for students. In addition to promoting authentic resources and facilitating asynchronous second language learning, this massive growth in mobile devices has advanced MALL by giving ESL students access to an informal learning platform outside of the classroom and allowing them to utilize their advantages for sessions for learning and instruction (Akara et al., 2020).

WhatsApp is among the most widely used apps on mobile devices. On social media, WhatsApp is renowned as a messenger app (Jasrial, 2019). Because it is simple to access from anywhere at any time, it is quite helpful for people learning a second language. WhatsApp has several tools, including voice messaging, video, and phone calls, which might help educators and students during teaching (Nurazizah et al., 2019). By simply hitting the voice message icon while speaking and forwarding it to the group chat on WhatsApp or privately, students can be given the task of audibly communicating with a teacher or friend about a certain subject by using the WhatsApp Voice Messaging tool.

Research on improving second language speaking abilities through informal learning with WhatsApp, as stated by Akkara et al. (2020), is not very broad. Therefore, it is

worthwhile to carry out more research on how WhatsApp Voice Messaging helps ESL students become more confident speakers. Speaking confidence has long been a problem for ESL students. Speaking in English with ESL learners requires consideration of their awareness of the significance of self-confidence, as noted by Tridinanti (2018). It should be simple for students to openly exchange ideas and communicate with one another in the setting for learning and teaching setting. Tridinanti (2018) added that if students struggle or are unable to speak English, they might find it challenging to explain themselves in a basic discussion in a second language. Using MALL with WhatsApp could aid students in improving their speaking abilities. According to Andujar-Vaca and Cruz (2017), mobile social contact and participation are becoming a more important instrument in the development of second languages and are creating an educational tool that teachers have not yet fully utilized.

Problem Statement

In many English learning environments, especially where English is not the primary language, students have limited opportunities to practice speaking skills during class time. This lack of sufficient spoken interaction hinders their ability to develop their proficiency in oral communication. Traditional classroom settings often prioritize reading and writing, leaving a gap in speaking practice. Furthermore, inadequate use of technology and supplementary resources further contributes to this problem (Namaziandost, 2019). Given these challenges, there is a need to explore alternative methods to support students' speaking development beyond the classroom. This study aims to investigate the effectiveness of WhatsApp as a supplementary tool to enhance students' English speaking skills outside formal learning settings.

Aim of the Study

The aim of this study is to know the effectiveness of using WhatsApp for improving

the English speaking skills of university students.

Objectives of the Study

1. To analyze the effectiveness of using WhatsApp for improving English speaking skills.
2. To examine the significant difference in pre- and post-speaking tests before and after using WhatsApp for improving English speaking skills.

Research Questions

- Q1. How effective is the use of WhatsApp for improving the English speaking skills of university students?
- Q2. Is there any significant difference in pre- and post-speaking tests before and after using WhatsApp for improving English speaking skills?

Research Hypothesis

H_0 There is no significant difference between pre- and post-intervention English speaking test scores after using WhatsApp for practice.

Significance of the Study

WhatsApp is one of the modern teaching and learning tools that stimulates the curiosity of many scholars. As a result, a lot of research has been done on the application of these techniques in English-speaking instruction and acquisition. The results of this study will be useful for curriculum designers, teachers, and students in the educational environment. It demonstrates the actual impact of utilising WhatsApp for educational purposes and on the stakeholders that were previously mentioned. It will facilitate greater communication and engagement between educators and students, as well as help teachers in assessing the growth of learners. Additionally, WhatsApp's voice feature, which connects students with native speakers or other proficient language learners, can support independent and productive study sessions. It could be a step toward bettering the educational and desired objectives, as well as our English language curriculum for curriculum creators.

Literature Review

Mobile Assisted Language Learning

According to [Kukulka-Hulme \(2013\)](#), p. 3701, MALL is the application of "mobile technology to the acquisition of languages, particularly scenarios in which device portability offers specific advantages." It is the use of mobile devices for language instruction and acquisition. This trend has made room for a new way of learning that is unaffected by traditional methods. It's a method that goes into detail on using mobile devices to study languages. MALL describes how devices and cell phones can support language acquisition ([Valamarthi, 2011](#)).

WhatsApp in language teaching

WhatsApp is an instant messaging application for social media that allows users to share videos, photos, phone calls, and text messages. There are currently over two billion WhatsApp users worldwide. The reality is this app is free and easy to install on several smartphone kinds, making it accessible to a wide range of consumers ([Montag et al., 2015](#)).

Because of these characteristics, an increasing number of researchers have investigated its potential for language teaching and learning.

Several studies have investigated the attitudes and perceptions of language learners regarding the use of WhatsApp for increasing the teaching and learning of foreign languages ([Alqahtani, Bhaskar, Elumalai & Abumelha, 2018](#); [Ali & Bin-Hady, 2019](#); [Han & Keskin, 2016](#); [Hamad, 2018](#)).

Students were observed to have generally favorable attitudes and perceptions about using WhatsApp. The potential use of WhatsApp as an asynchronous CMC tool to enhance language learners' speaking abilities has been investigated in two studies ([Andújar-Vaca & Cruz-Martínez, 2017](#); [Akkara, Anumula & Mallampalli, 2020](#)). For six months, [Andújar-Vaca and Cruz-Martínez \(2017\)](#) employed WhatsApp as an extracurricular pursuit to teach Spanish language learners how to speak. It has

been proven that WhatsApp audio messages greatly aid in improving the speaking ability of their Spanish students.

WhatsApp's effect on English language learning

Numerous studies have examined how WhatsApp affects students' ability to improve their English language learning (Ahmed, 2019; Andujar, 2016; Alsaleem, 2013; Asif, 2018; Nasr & Mustafa, 2018). Ahmed (2019) investigated how WhatsApp affected the reading and writing proficiency of twenty English as a Foreign Language learners at Aden University in the Yemeni environment. The results showed that WhatsApp helps pupils stay motivated and gives them chances to improve their writing and reading abilities. In addition, a research investigation was carried out in the Iranian context to examine the influence of WhatsApp on students' vocabulary acquisition about its effect on language learning. Eighty English as a Foreign Language learners were divided into experimental and control groups. Whereas the experimental group received vocabulary instruction via a WhatsApp group, the control group received instruction in a face-to-face traditional educational environment. Mahdi (2018) discovered some evidence that students' usage of WhatsApp contributed to the growth of their vocabulary. Another study looked specifically at gender about WhatsApp among Jordanian students. According to the findings, women performed better than men in writing (Bataineh, Al-Hamad, & Al-Jamal, 2018). In summary, WhatsApp has been shown to have favorable effects on students' English language acquisition in all of the studies mentioned above.

Enhancing Speaking through WhatsApp

Speaking is a complex and active ability with cognitive, physical, and sociocultural components, according to Burns (2019). The author also noted that speaking necessitates the quick activation of a speaker's abilities and knowledge in the present time. Thus, speaking should be taught in language classes, with an emphasis on involving students in speaking

exercises and developing effective communication techniques, according to Burns (2019). Additionally, Alysouf (2021) found that voice recordings significantly affect speaking abilities, particularly pronunciation.

Fluency is a crucial component of speaking abilities, as Sánchez (2019) noted in her research. Le (2018) similarly focused on fluency and the complexity in his research of how students practiced speaking while recording their voices and what effects this had on language proficiency.

Teaching Speaking by Voice Chatting through WhatsApp

Making language learners happy to speak in the target language is the process of teaching speaking. Many different things may be done to encourage students to be willing to practice speaking in front of an audience. Using WhatsApp for voice chat is one of them. Using a computer or a mobile device to communicate in real time is known as voice chatting. With this type of activity, students can engage in real-time communication outside of the classroom, much as they would with their friends regularly. Within an online, semi-formal context, they can be prompted to take their time when conversing, exchanging information, or expressing thoughts to their groups.

Theoretical Framework: Uses and Gratifications Theory

The theoretical foundation of this study is the Uses and Gratifications Theory, also called Needs and Gratifications Theory. It is a model that focuses on why people use certain media rather than other media. The uses and gratifications theory was propounded by Elihu Katz, Jay Blumler and Michael Gurevitch in 1974. According to Daniel (2010), the uses and gratifications model posits that audience members have certain needs or drives that are satisfied by using both non-media and media sources.

Methodology

To get reliable outcomes and draw valid conclusions from the study, the quantitative

research approach was employed throughout the data collection and data analysis.

One one-group pretest and posttest design was used for this study. A main instrument for data collection was the IELTS speaking test, adopted from official IELTS practice materials provided by the British Council. The IELTS speaking band descriptors were used as a scoring rubric, focusing on fluency and coherence, grammatical range, accuracy and pronunciation.

To ensure validity, the test questions were adapted from authentic IELTS materials and aligned with the study's objectives. Reliability was established through inter-rater reliability: two trend English teachers independently rated all responses, and any discrepancies in scoring were discussed and resolved.

By using a purposive sampling technique, 100 Participants are selected from the English department of Shaheed Benazir Bhutto University, Sanghar Campus. Every participant has a smartphone, and they all use WhatsApp for learning and regular communication. The respondents were learning English as a second language, ranged in age from 22 to 26 years. The pre- and post-tests were conducted on 100 individuals by WhatsApp voice messaging. The spoken versions were recorded, coded, and stored on a computer drive. The pretest and posttest recordings, collected via WhatsApp voice message, were first evaluated using the IELTS speaking Rubric, a standardized 9- point scale where 1 indicates very low proficiency and 9 indicates very high proficiency. Each recording was assessed across four components: fluency and coherence, lexical resource, grammatical range and accuracy and pronunciation. After ovulation, the qualitative voice data were converted into quantitative scores based on the rubric. These numerical scores were then organized and entered into SPSS software for statistical analysis. After that, a descriptive analysis and a paired sample T-test are used in the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

Findings and Discussions

Q1. How effective is the use of WhatsApp for improving the English speaking skills of university students?

Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Posttest Fluency	100	5.00	8.00	6.8000	.80403
Posttest Pronunciation	100	5.00	8.00	6.6900	1.08892
Posttest Lexical	100	4.00	8.00	6.3700	1.23628
Posttest Grammar	100	4.00	8.00	6.3500	.96792
Pretest Grammar	100	3.00	8.00	5.7900	1.19168
Pretest Lexical	100	3.00	8.00	5.5500	1.51341
Pretest Pronunciation	100	4.00	7.00	5.2100	.86801
Pretest Fluency	100	3.00	7.00	4.9800	.98453
Valid N (list-wise)	100				

This table of descriptive statistics showing effectiveness of WhatsApp in pre- to post-test scores in four components of English speaking skills: fluency, pronunciation, lexical resources and grammar.

Fluency

The mean score for fluency improves from 4.98 in the pretest to 6.80 in the posttest, indicating a substantial increase of 1.82 points. This highlights significant progress in the student's ability to speak fluently.

Pronunciation

The mean score of pronunciation increased from 5.21 in the pre-test to 6.69 in the post-test. Showing an improvement of 1.48, reflecting better clarity in speech.

Lexical Resource

The mean score for Lexical resource rose from 5.55 in the pre-test to 6.37 in the post-test, a gain of 0.82, demonstrating enhancement in the use of vocabulary during speaking tasks.

Grammar

The mean score for grammar improved from 5.79 in pre-test to 6.35 in post-test, indicating an

increase of 0.56 points. This suggests progress in grammatical accuracy and sentence structure.

The results show that the most significant improvements were in fluency and pronunciation, while lexical resources and grammar also exhibited noticeable gains. These findings underscore the effectiveness of the intervention in enhancing students' speaking skills.

Paired Samples Statistics

The paired sample statistics reveal significant mean score improvement across all evaluated aspects of English-speaking skills and the overall band score. Each component demonstrates progress, highlighting the effectiveness of the intervention.

Fluency

For fluency, the mean score increased from 4.98 in the pretest to 6.80 in the posttest, representing the largest improvement of 1.82 points. This significant gain underscores the enhanced ability of students to speak smoothly.

Pronunciation

In terms of pronunciation, the mean score rose from 5.21 in the pretest to 6.69 in the posttest test showing a notable improvement of 1.48 points. This enhancement indicates that

Paired Samples Statistics					
		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	Pre-test Pronunciation	5.2100	100	.86801	.08680
	Post-test Pronunciation	6.6900	100	1.08892	.10889
Pair 2	Pre-test Grammar	5.7900	100	1.19168	.11917
	Post-test Grammar	6.3500	100	.96792	.09679
Pair 3	Pre-test Lexical	5.5500	100	1.51341	.15134
	Post-test Lexical	6.3700	100	1.23628	.12363
Pair 4	Pre-test Fluency	4.9800	100	.98453	.09845
	Post-test Fluency	6.8000	100	.80403	.08040
Pair 5	Pre-test Bands	5.0350	100	.82955	.08296
	Post-test bands	6.6450	100	.90814	.09081

students become more proficient in articulating words clearly and accurately during the intervention.

Lexical resource

The Lexical resource score also demonstrated progress, with the mean increasing from 5.55 in the pretest to 6.37 in the posttest, marking an improvement of 0.82 points. This reflects better vocabulary usage and word selection during speaking tasks, enabling students to communicate more effectively.

Grammar

For grammar, the mean score improved from 5.79 in the pretest to 6.35 in the posttest test a moderate increase of 0.56 points. This suggests advancements in students' grammatical accuracy and their ability to construct sentences correctly.

Overall Bands Score

Finally, the overall band score, which combines all components, increased from 5.04 in the pretest to 6.65 in the posttest, indicating a substantial improvement of 1.61 points. This overall enhancement highlights the development of students' speaking skills across all evaluated areas.

Q2. Is there any significant difference in pre and post speaking test before and after using WhatsApp for improving English speaking skills?

Paired Samples Test

Paired Samples Test									
		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	Pre-test Pronunciation - Post-test Pronunciation	1.4800	.59425	.05942	-1.59791	1.36209	24.905	9	.000
Pair 2	Pre-test Grammar - Post-test Grammar	.5600	.75639	.07564	-.71008	.40992	7.4049	9	.000
Pair 3	Pre-test Lexical - Post-test Lexical	.8200	1.11355	.11136	-1.04095	.59905	7.3649	9	.000
Pair 4	Pre-test Fluency - Post-test Fluency	1.8200	.57525	.05753	-1.93414	1.70586	31.639	9	.000
Pair 5	Pre-test Bands - Post-test bands	1.6100	.40564	.04056	-1.69049	1.52951	39.690	9	.000

The paired samples test results indicate statistically significant improvements in the mean scores of all evaluated components of English-speaking skills and the overall band score. The mean differences reflect the progress from pretest to posttest, with a p-value confirming the significance of these changes.

Pronunciation

For pronunciation, the mean differences between pretest and posttest scores are 1.48, indicating a notable enhancement in pronunciation skills.

The p-value is .000, demonstrating that this improvement is highly statistically significant and not due to random variation.

Grammar

In the case of grammar, the mean difference is 0.56, reflecting improvement in grammatical accuracy. The p-value of .000 confirms the statistical significance of this progress, showing that the intervention had a meaningful impact on students' grammar skills.

Lexical resource

For lexical resource, the mean score is 0.82, indicating a significant increase in students' lexical resource. This improvement is supported by a p-value of .000, reinforcing that the changes are significant to the intervention.

Fluency

Fluency demonstrates the largest mean improvement with a difference of 1.82, reflecting substantial progress in students' speaking fluency. The corresponding p-value of .000 confirms the high statistical significance of enhancement.

Overall Bands Score

Finally, the overall band score exhibits a mean improvement, with a difference of 1.61, highlighting comprehensive improvement across all speaking components. The p-value of .000 indicates that this overall advancement is statistically significant and a result of the intervention.

The consistently significant p values (less than .05) for all components confirm that the

observed improvements in mean score are not due to chance, demonstrating the effectiveness of the intervention in improving students' speaking skills.

Data Reliability

Scale: Pretest and Posttest pronunciation

Case Processing Summary			
		N	%
Cases	Valid	100	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	100	100.0

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.900	2

100 cases (participants) were included in the analysis, representing 100% of the data. All participants had complete data for both pretest and posttest pronunciation scores. No cases were excluded (0 cases, 0%). This means there was no missing data, and all participants' data were used.

Cronbach's Alpha (0.900) indicates a high level of reliability. Values above 0.7 are considered acceptable, and values close to our above 0.9 suggest excellent reliability. In this context, the pretest and postcard scores are consistent and measure the same construct (pronunciation skills) effectively.

Scale: Pretest and Posttest Grammar

Case Processing Summary			
		N	%
Cases	Valid	100	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	100	100.0

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.862	2

All 100 participants had complete data for the pretest and posttest grammar scores, no data were missing. No cases were excluded from the analysis.

Cronbach's Alpha (0.862) indicates a high level of reliability. In this case value of 0.862

suggests the pretest and posttest grammar scores are consistent and reliable in measuring Grammar skills.

Scale: Pretest and Posttest Lexical

Case Processing Summary			
		N	%
Cases	Valid	100	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	100	100.0

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.806	2

All 100 participants' data were included in the analysis, meaning every case had complete data for both pretest and posttest lexical scores. No data was missing, so no cases were excluded from the analysis. Cronbach's Alpha (0.806) indicates good reliability. A value of 0.7 is generally considered acceptable, and a value of 0.806 reflects strong internal consistency between the pretest and posttest scores, meaning the measurements are reliable.

Scale: Pretest and Posttest Fluency

Case Processing Summary			
		N	%
Cases	Valid	100	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	100	100.0

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.886	2

All 100 participants provided complete data for both pretest and posttest fluency scores, so no data were missing and no cases were excluded from the analysis.

Cronbach's Alpha (0.886) indicates high reliability. A value close to 0.9, like 0.886, demonstrates strong internal consistency. This means the pretest and posttest fluency scores reliably measure fluency.

Discussion

Mahdi (2018) discovered evidence that students' use of WhatsApp contributed to vocabulary growth, aligning with the findings of

this research. This study's results similarly demonstrate that WhatsApp enhances students' vocabulary, which has been reflected in the pre- and posttest analyses showing a notable increase in lexical competence among participants. These findings affirm that WhatsApp's informal and interactive setting provides students with continuous exposure to new vocabulary, supporting vocabulary development beyond the classroom.

Furthermore, Alyouf (2021) emphasized that voice recording techniques could improve students' vocabulary and fluency. This study validates this assertion, as the use of WhatsApp's voice messaging feature enabled students to participate and refine their spoken English in a relaxed environment, positively impacting their fluency and confidence. This result underscores how incorporating voice recording tools, like WhatsApp voice notes, facilitates repetitive practice, thereby enhancing students' oral proficiency.

Cameron (2001) highlighted essential skills required for effective speaking, including vocabulary, pronunciation, grammar and comprehension. The findings of this study confirmed that WhatsApp provides an advantageous platform for developing these core speaking skills. The improvements observed in participants' fluency, grammatical accuracy, and vocabulary underscore WhatsApp's effectiveness in fostering these critical areas. Additionally, as Hornby (2006) noted, pronunciation is vital for conveying sound and pronunciation accurately, allowing for clear communication. The participant's progress in pronunciation aligns with this observation, indicating that frequent speaking practice on WhatsApp can help improve pronunciation skills.

The positive outcomes from this study demonstrate that mobile-assisted language learning (MALL) tools like WhatsApp can significantly bridge the gap caused by limited classroom exposure to spoken English. These

findings suggest that WhatsApp can indeed serve as an effective supplement to traditional language instruction, offering students greater opportunities for interactive, informal learning and enhancing their speaking abilities outside formal educational settings.

Conclusion

The findings reveal a statistically significant improvement in students' speaking skills, specifically in areas such as fluency (Mean - Pretest 4.9800, Posttest 6.8000), grammar (Mean- Pretest 5.7900, Posttest 6.3500), and lexical resources (Mean – Pretest 5.5500, Posttest 6.3700). The study confirms that the structured and consistent use of WhatsApp voice messaging promotes spoken language development by providing Learners with opportunities to practice, receive input and reflect on their language used in a low-pressure setting. Furthermore, the integration of Mobile Assistant language learning tools, such as WhatsApp, addresses the limited classroom time often available for speaking practice, offering a flexible, centred alternative.

In light of these findings, it is recommended that educators consider incorporating mobile-based platforms like WhatsApp into their language teaching strategies to create more immersive and interactive Learning experiences. While the results are promising, the study is limited by a one-group design and focuses on one institution. Future research should consider a Larger and more diverse sample, comparative groups, and a longer intervention period to further validate the effectiveness of WhatsApp and explore its impact on other language skills.

Reference

- Akkara, S., Anumula, V., & Mallampalli, M. (2020). Impact of WhatsApp interaction on improving L2 speaking skills. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (ijet)*, 15(3), 250-259.
- Alsyouf, A., & Al Kayed, M. (2021). An interactive intervention strategy for English as a foreign language classes versus traditional methods to teach speaking. *Studies in English Language and Education*, 8(2), 479-491.
- Amelia, M. (2020). WHATSAPP GOES TO CLASSROOM: USING WHATSAPP TO FOSTER STUDENTS ' SPEAKING SKILLS IN SPEECH. *Proceeding Iain Batusangkar*, 1(3), 153-158.
- Andújar-Vaca, A., & Cruz-Martínez, M.-S. (2017). Mobile instant messaging: WhatsApp and its potential to develop oral skills. *Comunicar*, 25(50), 43-52.
- Andujar, A. (2016). Benefits of mobile instant messaging for developing ESL writing. *System*, 62, 63-76.
- Asif, M. (2018). Mobile-assisted language learning (MALL): Use of WhatsApp as an effective tool to support ESL/EFL writing skills. *Remarking an Analysis*, 3(9), 112-114.
- Ariebowo, T. (2021). Autonomous learning during the COVID-19 pandemic: Students' objectives and preferences. *Journal of Foreign Language Teaching and Learning*, 6(1), 56-77.
- Bataineh, R. F., Al-Hamad, R. F., & Al-Jamal, D. A. (2018). Gender and EFL writing: Does WhatsApp make a difference? *Teaching English with Technology*, 18(2), 21-33.
- Burns, A. (2019). Concepts for teaching speaking in the English language classroom. *LEARN Journal: Language Education and Acquisition Research Network*, 12(1), 1-11.
- Cameron, L. (2001). Teaching languages to young learners. *Cambridge UP*.
- Elhadi, N. (2018). The Impact of YouTube, Skype and WhatsApp in Improving EFL Learners' Speaking Skills. *International Journal of Contemporary Applied Research*, 5(5), 18-31.
- Gamage, K. A., Silva, E. K. d., & Gunawardhana, N. (2020). Online delivery and assessment during COVID-19: Safeguarding academic integrity. *Education Sciences*, 10(11), 301.
- Gurler, I. (2015). Correlation between self-confidence and speaking skills of English language teaching and English language and literature preparatory students. *Curr Res Soc Sci*, 1(2), 14-19.
- Hamad, M. M. (2017). Using WhatsApp to Enhance Students' Learning of the English Language: " Experience to Share". *Higher Education Studies*, 7(4), 74-87.

- Han, T., & Keskin, F. (2016). Using a mobile application (WhatsApp) to reduce EFL speaking anxiety. *Gist: Education and Learning Research Journal*(12), 29-50.
- Jasrial, D. (2019). Utilising WhatsApp application for teaching the English language: Why and how? International Seminar and Annual Meeting BKS-PTN Wilayah Barat,
- Kartal, G. (2019). What's up with WhatsApp? A critical analysis of mobile instant messaging research in language learning. *International Journal of Contemporary Educational Research*, 6(2), 352-365.
- Katz, E., Blumler, J. G., & Gurevitch, M. (1973). Uses and gratifications research. *The public opinion quarterly*, 37(4), 509-523.
- Kukulska-Hulme, A. (2016). Mobile assistance in language learning: A critical appraisal.
- Le, T. (2018). Voice Recording in a second language outside the classroom: Process and product. *Journal of NELTA*, 23(1-2), 129-141.
- Mahdi, H. S. (2018). Effectiveness of mobile devices on vocabulary learning: A meta-analysis. *Journal of educational computing research*, 56(1), 134-154.
- Matthew O. Ward, G. G., Daniel Keim. (2015). *Interactive Data Visualisation, Foundations, Techniques, and Applications*.
- Mantra, I. B. N., Astawa, I. N., & Widiastuti, I. A. M. S. (2018). Integrating Innovative Experiential Learning in Cyclic Teaching Sessions of English Speaking Classes. *SOSHUM: Jurnal Sosial Dan Humaniora*, 8(2), 185-190.
- Montag, C., Błaszkiwicz, K., Sariyska, R., Lachmann, B., Andone, I., Trendafilov, B., Eibes, M., & Markowetz, A. (2015). Smartphone usage in the 21st century: who is active on WhatsApp? *BMC research notes*, 8, 1-6.
- Mustafa, E. N. E. (2018). The impact of YouTube, Skype and WhatsApp on improving EFL learners' speaking skills. *International Journal of Contemporary Applied Research*, 5(5), 18-31.
- Namaziandost, E., & Nasri, M. (2019). The impact of social media on EFL learners' speaking skills: a survey study involving EFL teachers and students. *Journal of Applied Linguistics and Language Research*, 6(3), 199-215.
- Nurazizah, H., Friatin, L. Y., & Sugiarto, B. R. (2019). WhatsApp voice note in a speaking class. *Journal of English Education and Teaching*, 3(3), 343-360.
- Sánchez Vaca, S. V. (2019). Improving speaking fluency and self-confidence through timed monologue recordings in beginner EFL students.
- Tridinanti, G. (2018). The correlation between speaking anxiety, self-confidence, and speaking achievement of Undergraduate EFL students of a private university in Palembang. *International Journal of Education and Literacy Studies*, 6(4), 35-39.
- Widiastuti, I. A. M. S., Mukminatien, N., Prayogo, J. A., & Irawati, E. (2019). PERCEPTION OF ASSESSMENT AND FEEDBACK PRACTICES: MAKING LEARNING VISIBLE. *International Journal of Sustainability, Education, and Global Creative Economy (IJSEGCE)*, 2(1), 1-8.
- Xu, Q., & Peng, H. (2017). Investigating mobile-assisted oral feedback in teaching Chinese as a second language. *Computer Assisted Language Learning*, 30(3-4), 173-182.